
**RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY OF RESEARCH PAPERS PUBLISHED IN
CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS BY COLLEGE LIBRARIANS: SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO NANDURBAR DISTRICT (MS)**

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Abstract:

This studies paper posted in Conference proceeding identifies the elements that make a contribution to the fulfillment of librarians as lively researchers. Research fulfillment is commonly aligned with productiveness and output, and the authors are consequently interested by know-how the elements that inspire studies productiveness. This fills an opening with inside the literature on librarians as researchers. This paper present research productivity of LIS professionals in Kavyitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon Affiliated Colleges in Nandurbar District, during 2009-10 to 2018-19. This research paper covers the analysis of this paper is Year wise Research Productivity, research paper publication in state, national and International level conference proceedings, Gender-wise trend, Age-wise trend, Area-wise trend, Author trend, and Language-wise trend published in Conference Proceeding. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the information.

Keyword: *Research, Research Productivity, Research paper, Conference Proceeding, College Librarian.*

Introduction:

Research Productivity is the amalgamation of studies and productiveness. Research is a vigilant observe and productiveness is an output produced at some point of particular time period. It is an incessant method which facilitates to decide reality or reality. It facilitates to clear up questions, accumulate applicable data or data, produce outcomes after which on the idea of given outcomes pointers are given. It assists in making corrections and including up understanding. Research-primarily based totally understanding or data is

reasonable, lucid and experience-primarily based totally.

Research productiveness may be a crucial detail of librarians' profession improvement and profession progression; however, librarians' enthusiasm and ability to attain and preserve a scholarly file is inconsistent. While a few librarians have excelled on this element in their responsibilities, others have struggled (Walters, 2016; O'Brien & Cronin, 2016).^{1, 2} There had been several procedures to helping librarians of their efforts to be efficient researchers;

however, the effect of those helps has now no longer been properly studied.

The said researcher has studied the research productivity of the college librarians affiliated to the Kavyitri Bahinabai Chaudhary, Uttar Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. A total of ten academic years from 2009-10 to 2018-19 were studied. A total of 215 colleges in Dhule, Jalgaon and Nandurbar districts of Maharashtra have been studied. There are total 41 colleges in Nandurbar district out of which the post of librarian is not filled in 20 colleges and 4 colleges did not respond. Only 17 colleges filled the structured questionnaire and sent it.

Review of Literature:

Deshmukh (2019)3

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad the authors have studied the research productivity of librarians during the period of 15 years from 2000 to 2014. In the said research, out of total 86 grant-aided college librarians, 55 librarians from rural areas have written books, conference proceedings, articles in periodicals, newspapers and editorials, etc. In consideration of the author's publication in recent years, many formal analyzes have been presented in the literature describing the phenomenon of productivity in rural college librarians. An author's number of publications is considered here as a measure of author productivity.

Hoffmann, Berg, Kofojinakis (2017)4

For the quantitative study in this paper, the authors distributed an online survey to 1,653 college librarians across Canada and received a 27% response rate. The survey asked participants to report their research findings and answer questions about three types of factors, including personal characteristics,

community and organizational structures, and support. The research product was then run and statistically analyzed to identify the three categories, the factors within those categories, and the relationships between them.

Chikate and Wadhwa (2014)5

A study was conducted on research productivity of librarians of SNDT Women's University, Mumbai. During the study period from 2003 to 2012, librarians contributed to 71 publications. The year 2011 is the year with the highest research output. Most share is on library management. The majority of librarians are women and their research contribution is 99%. The researcher gave first preference to English language for research. Publication Single authorship is dominant over others. The most popular medium of communication is magazine. The most prolific writer is Dr. Sarika Sawant. It enumerates the number of college libraries in terms of rural and urban areas.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyze the research productivity of LIS professional during 2009-10 to 2018-19.
2. To find out the year wise research productivity.
3. To identify the profile author having largest number of publication.
4. To know research productivity in Conference Proceedings
5. To know gender wise research productivity.
6. To know language wise research productivity.

Scope and Limitation of the Study:

Present study is limited to 17 Academic College Librarians in Nandurbar district region which are

affiliate to Kavyitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon (MS).

is prominent with the aid of using its reliance upon the choice of character from massive and small populace and the making of observation. So that inference may be carried out to provide populace.

Research Methodology:

Present take a look at has executed with the assist of survey method. Survey studies

Table no. 1: Year wise Research Productivity in Conference Proceedings

Sr. No.	Year	Year wise written Research paper in Conference Proceedings	%	Cumulative %
1.	2009-10	01	0.82	0.82
2.	2010-11	04	3.28	4.10
3.	2011-12	13	10.66	14.76
4.	2012-13	10	8.20	22.96
5.	2013-14	14	11.47	34.43
6.	2014-15	21	17.21	51.64
7.	2015-16	12	9.84	61.48
8.	2016-17	18	14.75	76.23
9.	2017-18	13	10.66	86.89
10.	2018-19	16	13.11	100
Total		122	100	

Table no. 1. Shows the writing of research papers in conference proceedings from the study period 2009-10 to 2018-19 shows the research productivity by that year. The above table shows that 122 research papers have been written in conference

proceedings during the study period. The average number of research productivity per year is 12.2. Academic year 2014-15 has the highest 17.21% papers written in conference proceedings and the lowest 0.82% papers published in 2009-10.

Table no. 2: Year-wise trend of research paper publication in state, national and International level conference proceedings

S.N.	Year	Research Paper	State	%	National	%	International	%
1.	2009-10	01	00	00	01	0.82	00	00
2.	2010-11	04	00	00	04	3.28	00	00
3.	2011-12	13	04	3.28	07	5.74	02	1.64
4.	2012-13	10	00	00	09	7.38	01	0.82
5.	2013-14	14	01	0.82	11	9.01	02	1.64
6.	2014-15	21	05	4.10	14	11.47	02	1.64
7.	2015-16	12	01	0.82	08	6.56	03	2.46
8.	2016-17	18	02	1.64	10	8.20	06	4.92
9.	2017-18	13	01	0.82	09	7.38	03	2.46
10.	2018-19	16	01	0.82	09	7.38	06	4.92
Total		122	15	12.30	82	67.22	25	20.48

Table no. 2. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 shows the year-wise trend of writing of research papers in state, national and international

level conference proceedings. The above table shows that the respondents written 122 research papers in conference proceedings during the study period.

Respondents published 12.30% of research papers in state level conference proceedings during the research period with highest 4.10% in 2014-15 and lowest 0.82% in 2013-14, 2017-18 and 2018-19, national level conference proceedings. 67.22% of research papers are written. It is

highest at 11.47% in 2014-15 and lowest at 0.82% in 2009-10. 20.48% of research papers have been published in international level conference proceedings with the highest 4.92% in 2016-17 and 2018-19 and the lowest 0.82% in 2012-13.

Table no. 3: Genderwise Trends in writing of Research Papers in Conference

S.N.	Year	No. of Research Paper	Gender wise Trend			
			Male	%	Female	%
1.	2009-10	01	01	0.82	00	00
2.	2010-11	04	05	4.10	00	00
3.	2011-12	13	12	9.84	01	0.82
4.	2012-13	10	09	7.38	01	0.82
5.	2013-14	14	14	11.47	00	00
6.	2014-15	21	19	15.57	02	1.64
7.	2015-16	12	12	9.84	00	00
8.	2016-17	18	17	13.93	01	0.82
9.	2017-18	13	13	10.66	00	00
10.	2018-19	16	15	12.29	00	00
Total		122	117	95.90	05	4.10

Table no. 3. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 shows the gender wise trend of research paper publication in state, national and international level conference proceedings. The above table shows that 122 research papers were published in conference proceedings during this study period. Male respondents published 95.90% of research papers in conference

proceedings during the study period, with the highest 15.57% in 2014-15 and the lowest 0.82% in 2009-10; appeared Women respondents have published 4.10% of the research papers in conference proceedings during the study period and the highest was seen in 2014-15 at 1.64%, and the lowest at 0.82% in 2011-12, 2012-13 and 2016-17.

Table no. 4: Age-wise trends in writing of research papers in conference proceedings

S.N.	Year	Yearwise writing	Age-wise trends							
			23-30	%	31-40	%	41-50	%	51-60	%
1.	2009-10	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	01	0.82
2.	2010-11	04	00	00	00	00	02	1.64	02	1.64
3.	2011-12	13	00	00	02	1.64	05	4.10	06	4.92
4.	2012-13	10	00	00	01	0.82	03	2.46	06	4.92
5.	2013-14	14	00	00	02	1.64	07	5.74	05	4.10
6.	2014-15	21	00	00	03	2.46	08	6.56	10	8.20
7.	2015-16	12	00	00	06	4.92	02	1.64	04	3.28
8.	2016-17	18	00	00	10	8.20	01	0.82	07	5.74
9.	2017-18	13	00	00	10	8.20	01	0.82	02	1.64
10.	2018-19	16	00	00	07	5.74	04	3.28	05	4.10
Total		122	00	00	41	33.61	33	27.05	48	39.34

Table no. 4. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 the trend of writing of research papers in conference proceedings by age group. The above table shows that a total of 122 research papers have been written by the respondents in conference proceedings during the period. The table above shows that respondents aged 23-30 did not writing a paper in conference proceedings during the study. Respondents aged 31-40 have written 33.61% of research papers

during the study period, with the highest 8.20% in 2016-17 and 2017-18 and the lowest 0.82% in 2012-13. Respondents aged 41-50 written 27.05% of research papers during the study period, with the highest at 6.56% in 2014-15 and the lowest at 0.82% in 2016-17 and 2017-18. Respondents aged 51-60 written 39.34% of research papers during the study period with the highest 8.20% in 2014-15 and the lowest 0.82% in 2009-10.

Table no. 5: Areawise Trends in written of Research Papers in Conference Proceedings

Sr.No.	Year	Yearwise Publication	Areawise trend			
			Urban	%	Rural	%
1.	2009-10	01	01	0.82	00	00
2.	2010-11	04	02	1.64	02	1.64
3.	2011-12	13	07	5.74	06	4.92
4.	2012-13	10	06	4.92	04	3.28
5.	2013-14	14	09	7.38	05	4.10
6.	2014-15	21	15	12.29	06	4.92
7.	2015-16	12	08	6.56	04	3.28
8.	2016-17	18	13	10.65	05	4.10
9.	2017-18	13	12	9.84	01	0.82
10.	2018-19	16	13	10.65	03	2.45
Total		122	86	70.49	36	29.51

Table no. 5. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 shows the Area-wise trend of paper writing in state, national and international level conference proceedings. The above table shows the information about 122 research papers written in conference proceedings during this study period. Respondents from urban areas wrote 70.49% of papers

in conference proceedings during the study period and the highest was 12.29% in 2014-15, while the lowest was 0.82% in 2009-10. Respondents from rural areas wrote 29.51% of research papers during the study period, with the highest in 2011-12 and 2014-15 at 4.92% and the lowest at 0.82% in 2017-18.

Table no. 6: Author Trend of Research Paper Writing in State, National and International Level Conference Proceedings

S.N.	Year	Research Paper	One Author	%	Two Author	%	Three or more than author	%
1.	2009-10	01	01	0.82	00	00	00	00
2.	2010-11	04	03	2.46	01	0.82	00	00
3.	2011-12	13	12	9.84	01	0.82	00	00
4.	2012-13	10	09	7.38	01	0.82	00	00
5.	2013-14	14	11	9.02	03	2.46	00	00
6.	2014-15	21	14	11.47	06	4.91	01	0.82
7.	2015-16	12	08	6.56	03	2.46	01	0.82
8.	2016-17	18	10	8.20	05	4.10	03	2.46
9.	2017-18	13	07	5.73	05	4.10	01	0.82
10.	2018-19	16	09	7.38	05	4.10	02	1.64
Total		122	84	68.86	30	24.59	08	6.56

Table no. 6. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 shows the author wise trend of research paper writing in state, national and international level conference proceedings. The above table shows that during the study respondents authored 122 research papers in conference proceedings. During the research period, the respondents found that one Librarian wrote 68.86% of the conference proceedings with the highest

11.47% in 2014-15 and the lowest 0.82% in 2009-10, with two Librarians writing 24.59% of the conference proceedings. Found done. It is highest at 4.91% in 2014-15 and lowest at 0.82% from 2010-11 to 2013-14. Three or more Librarians jointly authored 6.56% of the papers in conference proceedings with the highest 2.46% in 2016-17 and the lowest 0.82% in 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2017-18.

Table no. 7: Linguistic Trends in Paper Writing in Conference Proceedings

S.N.	Year	Research Paper	Linguistic Trend							
			English	%	Hindi	%	Marathi	%	Other	%
1.	2009-10	01	00	00	00	00	01	0.82	00	00
2.	2010-11	04	04	3.28	01	0.82	01	0.82	00	00
3.	2011-12	13	09	7.38	00	00	02	1.64	00	00
4.	2012-13	10	09	7.38	00	00	01	0.82	00	00
5.	2013-14	14	11	9.02	00	00	03	2.46	00	00
6.	2014-15	21	15	12.29	00	00	06	4.91	00	00
7.	2015-16	12	11	9.02	00	00	01	0.82	00	00
8.	2016-17	18	17	13.93	00	00	00	00	00	00
9.	2017-18	13	12	9.84	00	00	01	0.82	00	00
10.	2018-19	16	15	12.29	00	00	02	1.64	00	00
Total		122	103	84.43	01	0.82	18	14.75	00	00

Table no. 7. According to the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19 there is a trend of language-wise research paper writing in conference proceedings. A total of 122 research papers have been written by the respondents in the conference proceedings during this period. The above table shows that 84.43% of the research papers were written by the respondents in English language during the study in conference proceedings. It has the highest number of 13.93% research papers written in 2016-17. Whereas in 2010-11, 3.28% research papers have been written. Respondents have written 0.82% dissertations in Hindi language during the study period, out of which 0.82% dissertations were written

only in 2010-11 but not in any other year. Respondents wrote 14.75% of research papers in Marathi during the study period, with the highest 4.91% in 2014-15 and the lowest 0.82% in 2009-10, 2010-11, 2012-13, 2015-16 and 2017-18. The research paper has been written. But during the study period, not a single research paper has been written in other languages.

Conclusion:

Although numerous challenges remain for librarian authors, the results of this study give publishing tips from academic librarians who are active scholars. Different conclusions are given as follows.

1. 122 research papers were written in conference proceedings during the study period, the academic year 2014-15 had the highest 17.21% papers written in conference proceedings and the lowest 0.82% papers written in 2009-10.
2. During the period 2009-10 to 2018-19 respondents have written the highest 67.22% national level, 20.48% international and 12.30% state level research papers in conference proceedings.
3. Male respondents have authored the highest 95.90% and female respondents 4.10% of conference proceedings during the study period from 2009-10 to 2018-19.
4. Respondents in the age group of 51-60 had the highest 39.34% followed by respondents in the age group of 31-40 with 33.61%, respondents in the age group of 41-50 with 27.05% and respondents in the age group of 23-30 did not do any writing.
5. During the period 2009-10 to 2018-19, 70.49% respondents from urban areas and 29.51% respondents from rural areas have written research papers in conference proceedings.
6. Most 84.43% of the respondents in English language followed by 14.75% respondents in Marathi language, 0.82% respondents in Hindi language have written research papers. While in other languages respondents have not written any research papers in conference proceedings.
7. During the period 2009-10 to 2018-19, respondents wrote the highest number of conference proceedings 68.86% with one Librarian, 24.59% with two Librarians and 6.56% with three or more Librarians.

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